

Unveiling the capacity of bioaugmentation application, in comparison with biochar and rhamnolipid for TPHs degradation in aged hydrocarbons polluted soil

Sandra Curiel-Alegre^{a,b}, Dalia de la Fuente-Vivas^a, Aqib Hassan Ali Khan^a, Javier García-Tojal^c, Blanca Velasco-Arroyo^d, Carlos Rumbo^a, Gerhard Soja^e, Carlos Rad^b, Rocío Barros^{a,*}

^a International Research Center in Critical Raw Materials for Advanced Industrial Technologies (ICCRAM), University of Burgos, Centro de I+D+I. Plaza Misael Bañuelos s/n, 09001 Burgos, Spain

^b Research Group in Composting (UBUCOMP), University of Burgos, Faculty of Sciences, Plaza Misael Bañuelos s/n, 09001 Burgos Spain

^c Department of Chemistry, University of Burgos, Faculty of Sciences. Plaza Misael Bañuelos s/n, 09001 Burgos, Spain

^d Department of Biotechnology and Food Science, University of Burgos, Faculty of Sciences, Plaza Misael Bañuelos s/n, 09001 Burgos Spain

^e Institute for Chemical and Energy Engineering, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Muthgasse 107, 1190, Vienna, Austria

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ABSTRACT

Persistent, aged hydrocarbons in soil hinder remediation, posing a significant environmental threat. While bioremediation offers an environmentally friendly and cost-effective approach, its efficacy for complex contaminants relies on enhancing pollutant bioavailability. This study explores the potential of immobilized bacterial consortia combined with biochar and rhamnolipids to accelerate bioremediation of aged total petroleum hydrocarbon (TPH)-contaminated soil. Previous research indicates that biochar and biosurfactants can increase bioremediation rates, while mixed consortia offer sequential degradation and higher hydrocarbon mineralization. The present investigation aimed to assess whether combining these strategies could further enhance degradation in aged, complex soil matrices. The bioaugmentation (BA) with bacterial consortium increased the TPHs degradation in aged soil (over 20% compared to natural attenuation - NA). However, co-application of BA with biochar and rhamnolipid higher did not show a statistically prominent synergistic effect. While biochar application facilitated the maintenance of hydrocarbon degrading bacterial consortium in soil, the present study did not identify a direct influence in TPHs degradation. The biochar application in contaminated soil contributed to TPHs adsorption. Rhamnolipid alone slightly increased the TPHs biodegradation with NA, while the combined bioaugmentation treatment with rhamnolipid and biochar increased the degradation between 27.5 and 29.8%. These findings encourage further exploration of combining bioaugmentation with amendment, like biochar and rhamnolipid, for remediating diverse environmental matrices contaminated with complex and aged hydrocarbons.

1. Introduction

Pollution with petroleum hydrocarbons remains a serious global problem, due to its widespread usage, occurrence, and persistence in the environment (Haider et al., 2021; Yousaf et al., 2022). This pattern of influence seems not to be affected in the recent future, as even today petroleum is the dominant global energy source (Khan et al., 2016a; Thirumurugan et al., 2023). Soil contamination due to total petroleum hydrocarbons (TPHs) is mainly affected by their weathering and aging process, that increased TPHs persistence in soil with reduced

photo-bio-transformation and volatilization (Hussain et al., 2022; Ellis et al., 2022). Therefore, to counteract the TPHs induced menace, identifying effective and economically viable remediation techniques is crucial. TPHs bioremediation is a promising strategy to remediate contaminated soils (Shukla et al., 2022; Udom et al., 2023). Bioremediation takes advantage of microbial (natural and augmented) capabilities to degrade oil (Khan et al., 2019; Manzoor et al., 2016). Bioremediation efficacy is dependent on the pollutants' type and their bioavailability, as well as the indigenous microbial community having capacity for bioremediation (Shahsavari et al., 2019; Khan et al., 2016b;

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: rbarros@ubu.es (R. Barros).

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Thomas et al., 2023). Nevertheless, oil contaminated soils are generally reported to show lower degradation efficiency due to decreased indigenous microbial diversity, low porosity, limited nutrients availability, and reduced moisture due to hydrophobicity (Zhang et al., 2019; Thomas et al., 2022).

As TPHs age evolves in contaminated soil, their breakdown becomes increasingly difficult (Bajagain and Jeong, 2021). Aged or weathered TPH presents unique challenges due to its complex harder-to-degrade composition, uneven distribution of hydrocarbon creating pockets of concentrated pollution, degraded soil structure limiting oxygen and nutrient flow, restricting microbial activity leading to nutrient imbalance, and trapped pollutants that are bound tightly to microscopic pore inside the soil particles making, them inaccessible to microbes (Rafique et al., 2023; Moured et al., 2023). Hussain et al. (2022) also proposed that this complex scenario due to hydrocarbon aging in soil presents a significant hurdle for effective TPHs bioremediation. In such a condition, the TPHs biodegradation can be improved by adding high-capacity adsorbents, such as activated carbon (AC) and biochar, right at the time of contamination, as they strongly adsorb hydrophobic compounds decreasing exposure risks and dispersion (Igun et al., 2019; Zahed et al., 2021). Further, numerous studies reported that pyrolyzed agricultural wastes can be used to immobilize microorganisms capable of degrading pollutants, that can be used as microbial population micro-factories in such a harsh environment (Lu et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2019). The use of biochar, as an immobilization carrier for biotechnological soil applications, has already prospered and established (Saravanan et al., 2023; Bolan et al., 2023; Thomas et al., 2024). Another potent amendment is the application of biosurfactants (amphiphilic compounds with a hydrophilic and hydrophobic moieties) which can increase hydrocarbon bioavailability and biodegradation of oil contaminants (Khan et al., 2017). Among different biosurfactants, the rhamnolipids (glycolipid biosurfactants), received considerable attention, due to their capacity to increase dissolution, bioavailability, and biodegradation of a wide range of contaminants in soils (Muthukumar et al., 2022a,b). Luo et al. (2024) also reported that the *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* WS02, capable of producing high amounts of rhamnolipids, can perform higher TPHs degradation. Similarly, Khan et al. (2017) also reported that the presence of biosurfactant in soil can lead to a higher TPHs degradation rate (up to ~28%). Further, rhamnolipid commercial production is also making this biosurfactant readily available to different industrial applications ranging from cleaning, food, agriculture, bioremediation, and even pharmaceuticals (Guzmán et al., 2023). Hence, it can be said that the combined application of these amendments in polluted soils, having aged TPHs, can also prove efficacious.

Many past studies employ artificially spiked TPHs, hindering understanding of real-world bioremediation for aged, contaminated soils (Hussain et al., 2022; Rafique et al., 2023). This research addresses this gap by investigating the impact of soil amendments (biochar and biosurfactants) on the treatment of aged petroleum hydrocarbons in soil, both individually and combined. Unlike limitations of traditional methods, this work utilizes a microbial consortium (isolated and optimized from the native soil), aligning with recent research advocating for biochar and biosurfactants to overcome bioavailability challenge of aged TPHs. Specifically, in this work, an aged, polluted soil with high levels of long-chain refractory hydrocarbons (C21-30) and co-presence of potentially harmful metal and metalloids, was used to study the impacts of new bioaugmentation approaches. Presently applied approach relied on use of two biochar, as microbial immobilization carriers, and a commercial rhamnolipid biosurfactant to increase hydrocarbon bioavailability. For 90 days, eight different approaches have been evaluated at a small-scale microcosm, including natural attenuation as a control, biostimulation using an improved nutrient formulation, biostimulation using two types of pyrolyzed biochar (BH1 and BH2), and rhamnolipids (RML), and the same approaches but with bioaugmentation. The study investigates aged, naturally occurring TPHs, which is more representative of real-world scenarios compared to

artificially spiked soils used in many previous studies, and employs a consortium isolated from the contaminated soil itself, potentially enhancing bioremediation efficacy compared to the use of non-native strains.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals and reagents

Aliphatic hydrocarbons: Alkanes-Mix 12, 100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ in toluene (C_7H_8), C8–C40 (pair no. of C, 17 HC) and polyaromatic hydrocarbons: PAHs-Mix 9, 100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ in cyclohexane (C_6H_{12}); 16 PAHs (EPA Method 610: acenaphthene, acenaphthylene, anthracene, benzo(a)anthracene, benzo(a)pyrene, benzo(b)fluoranthene, benzo(k)fluoranthene, benzo (g,h,i)perylene, chrysene, dibenzo (a,h)anthracene, fluoranthene, fluorene, indeno (1,2,3-c,d)pyrene, naphthalene, phenanthrene, and pyrene at 100 mg mL^{-1}) were purchased for chromatographic separation by LGC Standards Ltd (Teddington, UK). The certified reference materials CRM-357 (TPH–sandy loam), CRM-359 (TPH–clay) were acquired from Sigma-Aldrich (Burlington, Massachusetts, USA). Paraformaldehyde was used for scanning electron microscopy, produced by Sigma-Aldrich (P6148).

2.2. Soil description

Contaminated soil samples were obtained from a machinery park located in Noblejas (Toledo, Spain), at N 39° 58' and W 3° 24'. The soil under study was contaminated with a mixture of hydrocarbons, mineral oils, and heavy metals. Once the samples were collected, they were placed in clean, labeled containers and transported to the laboratory. Samples were air-dried and sieved at 2 mm for physicochemical characterization, using methods described Subsection 2.7 - Analytical methods. The results obtained for the initial soil were shown in Table 1.

2.3. Microbial consortia

The microorganisms used in this study were isolated from the contaminated soil, using the protocol outlined by Garrido-Sanz et al. (2019) and Curiel-Alegre et al. (2022a). Briefly, the microbial consortium was pre-inoculated in minimal medium (0.1 g L^{-1} NaCl, 0.1 g L^{-1} $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 1 g L^{-1} K_2HPO_4 , 0.5 g L^{-1} KH_2PO_4 , and 1 g L^{-1} $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$), supplemented with phosphate-buffered mineral medium salts (PAS) (2.5-times concentrated, 19.5 g L^{-1} MgSO_4 , 5 g L^{-1} KMnO_4 , H_2O , 1 g L^{-1} $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, and 0.3 g L^{-1} CaCl_2), 0.05% pre-filtered yeast extract (0.2 μm), 1% diesel, and incubated at 30 °C for 24 h at 180 RPMs. With the aim of studying the effect of microbial consortia on the

Table 1
Basic properties of initial polluted soil at the beginning of the experience.

Soil properties	Units	Initial Soil levels
Humidity	%	0.47
Field capacity	%	20.61
Bulk density	g cm^{-3}	1.683
Total carbon	%	6.447
Total nitrogen	%	0.021
Electrical conductivity	dS m^{-1}	0.801
pH (1:5 H_2O)	–	7.18
Organic matter	%	4.95
Clay	%	15.69
Silt	%	46.52
Sand	%	37.79
N- NO_3	mg Kg^{-1}	0.147
N- NH_3	mg Kg^{-1}	2.990
P- PO_4	mg Kg^{-1}	0.103
EPHs ^a	mg Kg^{-1}	4275

^a Composition of EPHs (%) C10–C12 = 0.20, C12–C16 = 4.99, C16–C21 = 4.23, C21–C30 = 50.68, C30–C35 = 31.19, and C35–C40 = 8.65.

hydrocarbon degradation, and the interaction between the organisms and the biochar (BH1 and BH2) or rhamnolipids (RML), the above protocol continued as detailed below.

To find out how the bacteria and biochar/rhamnolipids, individually or together, enhance hydrocarbon degradation, the microbial consortium was inoculated, and the suspension was centrifuged and pelleted (10 min at 500 RPMs) and resuspended in a 1:100 dilution for culture in 200 mL of minimal medium for 4 days. Once the pellets had been obtained from the pre-inoculum, it was resuspended in a modified Bushnell Haas Broth solution (BHB2). A final concentration of approximately 10^{11} CFU kg^{-1} soil was applied. This procedure was repeated twice just to perform two inoculations, on days 0 and 43. On the other hand, to analyze the interaction between bacteria and BH/RML, the flasks were then centrifuged at 4500 RPMs for 10 min and diluted 1:100 again in 1000 mL minimal medium and grown at 180 RPMs, 30 °C for 4 days. The culture (2.5 mL , 10^7 CFU mL^{-1}) was mixed with each BH or the RML (concentration equivalent to 1 g of soil). After 24 h at 100 RPMs, a FTIR-ATR analysis was performed.

2.4. Nutrient solution

A modified version of BHB2 solution was prepared for both bio-stimulation and bioaugmentation purposes according to Curiel-Alegre et al. (2022a). To achieve the desired nutrient levels, individual solutions were mixed, resulting in the final following amounts (g kg^{-1} dry soil): MgSO_4 0.0612, CaCl_2 0.0061, KH_2PO_4 0.3058, K_2HPO_4 0.3058, NH_4NO_3 3.5425, and FeCl_3 0.0153; the latest was added separately to prevent precipitation.

2.5. Organic supports and additives

Two types of biochar both obtained from apricot stones by pyrolysis at different temperatures, were provided and characterized by the AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH: Biochar 1 at 450 °C (BH1) and Biochar 2 at 600 °C (BH2). BH1 elemental composition was: 1.36% N, 74.13% C, 3.03% H, 0.03% S; Specific Surface Area (BET) $26.03 \pm 0.41 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$; EPA16-PAHs 0.027 mg kg^{-1} dry matter. BH2 elemental composition: 1.04% N, 83.50% C, 1.81% H, 0.00% S; Specific Surface Area (BET) $6.73 \pm 0.19 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$; EPA16-PAHs 0.032 mg kg^{-1} dry matter. Rhamnolipids (90% purity) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Saint Louis, Missouri USA).

2.6. Experimental design for the microcosms

Different soil mixtures were prepared for the different treatments adding 5% w/v of biochar (BH1 and BH2), 1% w/w of rhamnolipids, nutrient solution (BHB2), and inoculum, while water was added to achieve a moisture content of 40% of the water retention capacity (WRC), using a concrete mixer. On day 43, when the second consortia inoculation was conducted, the WRC was increased to 50%, utilizing this volume to incorporate water, the inoculum, or the nutrients solution. Eight treatments were established: control soil (abbreviated as CT), soil with BH1, soil with BH2, soil using RML as carriers, and these same treatments with the addition of the microbial consortium suspended in BHB-solution 2 (BACT, BABH1, BABH2, and BARML). The CT was a control to test natural attenuation effects on the bioremediated soil.

Approximately 200 g (dry basis) of soil mixtures were weighed and transferred to 1 L hermetic containers. Sampling was carried out at 0 (T0), 2 (T1), 15 (T2), 30 (T3), 45 (T4), 60 (T5), and 90 (T6) days of treatment. Three experimental replicates were introduced with a total of 144 soil microcosms, considering all sampling points and treatments. Each microcosm was opened twice a week to check moisture and was manually mixed to improve soil aeration. The containers were incubated in a climatic chamber at 22 ± 0.5 °C, in the dark. At each sampling point, one part of the soil was dried in an oven at 30 °C for 48 h, and the other part was immediately frozen at -20 °C until microbial analyses

were done.

2.7. Analytical methods

2.7.1. Soil physical and chemical analysis

The physicochemical characteristics of the soil were carried out as for the initial soil, using standard analytical methods, whereby all treatments were analyzed at the different sampling times to determine the evolution of their properties. A pH meter (GLP21, Crison) was used to determine the pH of soil through 5 g of sample and 25 mL of water (1:5, w:v) stirred at 60 RPMs for 30 min. Subsequently, the sample was centrifuged at 4000 RPMs for 20 min, filtered and measured in a conductivity meter (GLP31, Crison) to determine the electrical conductivity (EC). Nutrients were analyzed in an autoanalyzer (San++ Skalar, Breda, The Netherlands); available P was extracted from 2 g of soil with 40 mL of 0.5 M NaCO_3 at pH 8.5 which was shaken at 60 RPMs for 30 min, filtered, analyzed and quantified by the molybdenum blue method for orthophosphate; nitrate and soluble ammonium were extracted from 10 g of soil with 40 mL of 0.5 M K_2SO_4 stirred at 60 RPMs for 45 min, filtered, analyzed and quantified by Griess reaction after reduction on Cu–Cd column for nitrate, and by the indophenol blue method for ammonium. This extract was also used to analyze organic C and total N using the TOC-V CSN autoanalyzer (Shimadzu, Japan). Other nutrients and trace elements were determined from extracts of 2 g of soil with 20 mL of Mehlich3 extractant solution (0.2 M CH_3COOH , 0.001 M EDTA, 0.013 M HNO_3 , 0.015 M NH_4F , and 0.25 M NH_4NO_3), was shaken at 120 RPMs for 5 min, centrifuged at 4000 RPMs for 10 min and filtered prior to analysis using an ICP-OES (Genesis, Spectro, Germany). As the main objective of this manuscript is TPHs degradation, while the HMs were analyzed, no significant changes in the levels were observed from the initial to final HMs content in soil, however the information regarding HMs was presented in Supplementary table 1. Basal soil respiration (BSR) after 20 g of frozen soil was tempered for 72 h at 22 ± 0.5 °C, then placed in a 1 L jar with a tight seal together with a beaker containing 4 mL of 0.5 M NaOH, which acted as a gas trap, and incubated for 24 h. Then 2 mL of 0.5 M BaCl_2 was added, causing precipitation of adsorbed CO_2 as barium carbonate, and finally the remaining NaOH was quantified with standardized 0.1 M HCl solution using an automatic titrator (718 Stat Titrimo, Metrohm, Switzerland).

2.7.2. Scanning electron microscopy

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to visualize the bacterial adhesion onto the biochar. The consortium growth and subsequent incubation with both forms of biochar were carried out as explained above. After the samples had been incubated reaching maximal growth, they were centrifuged at 4000 RPMs for 10 min, rinsed in phosphate-buffered saline without calcium and magnesium (DPBS), and fixed for 30 min in 4% (v/v) paraformaldehyde in 0.1 M phosphate buffer at pH 7.4. After fixation, samples were washed twice with DPBS, and dehydrated for 10 min in 50, 70, 90, and 100% (v/v) ethanol. Finally, the samples were coated with a gold layer and analyzed in a scanning electron microscope SEM (FEI-Quanta 200F, Thermo Fisher, USA), in collaboration with “Parque Científico Universidad de Valladolid”.

2.7.3. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy - attenuated total reflectance (FTIR-ATR)

The bacterial consortium was concentrated 24 times in BHB medium to expose it to BH1, BH2, and RML at 1% soil concentration for 24 h at 100 RPMs and room temperature (final volume 2.5 mL). The supernatant was removed and washed three times with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) after shaking 5 min. Before associating bacterial consortium growth to biochar and rhamnolipids by studying their functional groups, the samples were ground and lyophilised. The functional groups present in the samples were studied by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy - attenuated total reflectance (FTIR-ATR), which can be useful to elucidate the kind and abundance of chemical compounds derived from

xylochemical (Groß et al., 2021) in the studied biochars, together with the changes in composition at different pyrolytic temperatures and the microorganism association. The spectra were recorded in the 4000-400 cm^{-1} region, with a spectral resolution of 4 cm^{-1} and 128 scans per spectrum, by a JASCO FT-IR 4200 spectrophotometer with an Attenuated Total Reflection ATR PRO ONE device. Graphics were depicted by Kaleidagraph v4.1.1 Synergy Software.

2.7.4. Gas chromatograph (GC) - Flame Ionization Detector (FID)

Soil extraction of EPHs was conducted using a modified version of the method outlined in Curiel-Alegre et al. (2022b). For 20 min at 150 °C, 1 g dried soil sample was combined with 20 ml 1:1 (v/v) acetone-hexane mixture and processed in a microwave oven (Milestone Ethos X, Italy). The resulting sample was centrifuged (4500 RPMs for 30 min), the supernatant filtered (0.22 μm), and concentrated to 1 mL using a rotary evaporator (Thermo SAVANT, SPD111V). Fractionation of extracted EPHs was achieved with Isolute EPH cartridges (5 mL 1 g^{-1}) pre-conditioned with hexane. Aliphatic and aromatic hydrocarbons were eluted separately using hexane and DCM (dichloromethane) respectively, at a flow rate of 2–3 mL min^{-1} . For analysis, the extracted fractions were concentrated using a nitrogen stream evaporation technique and injected into a GC-FID system (Varian 3900, USA) equipped with a Varian CP8907 capillary column (25 m long, 0.25 mm internal diameter, and with a 0.25- μm film thickness). Details regarding the operating condition and calculations are provided in the supplementary material (Text S1).

2.8. Statistical analysis

For the variables analyzed in this study, the mean and standard deviation of at least three separate experimental replicates were calculated. The data of the different treatments and times were analyzed by one-way ANOVA with various levels of significance, after checking for normality and homoscedasticity assumptions, using Prism 8.0

(GraphPad). Further to study and identify the statistically significance for to assess whether the applied variable (BA, BH1, BH2, and RML) have major effect with reference to varying time and is there any interaction among the applied variable, two-way ANOVA was applied. Network analysis was performed in JASP (v 0.18.1.0), where the graphs created positioned nodes (soil characteristics and concentration of TPHs) and edges (interrelationships) to reflect their strength of connection. The explanation for this network analysis was inferred with the findings in two-way ANOVA.

3. Results

3.1. Soil and organic amendments characterization and microcosm preparation

Basic properties of the soil under study can be seen in Table 1. Among the analyzed parameters for initial soil sample, included soil pH, EC, humidity, water content at field capacity, bulk density, particle size distribution, and organic matter. Further the NO_3 , NH_4 , and PO_4 were also analyzed. The total petroleum hydrocarbons (TPHs) were 4275 mg kg^{-1} and regarding mol wt. distribution of TPHs, a predominance of heaviest mol fractions is clearly shown. Soil pH values increased throughout the incubation for treatments in which the microbial consortium was not added (reaching to 7.84, 7.82, 7.85, 7.76 for CT, BH1, BH2, and RML, respectively), whereas for those in which the consortium was added (BACT, BABH1, BABH2, and BARML) soil pH decreased and remained at 6.56 ± 0.06 (Fig. 1a). This decrease in the bioaugmentation treatments may have been favorable for the solubility of nutrients, such as P and other trace elements. Electrical conductivity (EC) results did not show significant differences throughout the incubation (Fig. 1b). Slight variations appeared for the bioaugmentation treatments, except for BABH1, in which EC values increased with the addition of the microbial consortium and a decrease was observed over time due to higher microbial consumption in the soil.

Fig. 1. Evolution of soil chemical properties during incubation: (a) pH (Aq. 1:5 w/v); (b) Electrical conductivity (Aq. 1:5 w/v, 25 °C); (c) Extractable organic carbon (EOC); (d) Extractable total nitrogen (ETN); and (e) Available P. Treatments: CT, control soil, BH1, soil and 5% biochar 450 °C, BH2, soil and 5% biochar 600 °C; RML, soil and 1% rhamnolipids; BACT, bioaugmented control soil; BABH1, bioaugmented soil and 5% biochar 450 °C; BABH2, bioaugmented soil and 5% biochar 600 °C; BARML, bioaugmented soil and 1% rhamnolipids. Mean values \pm standard deviation.

The extractable organic C (EOC) showed a different behaviour depending on the treatment as shown in Fig. 1 c, although the greatest differences were observed in the bioaugmentation treatments. In the BACT and BABH1 treatments, a slow increase was observed, during incubation, and BABH2 reached a significant increase at day 45 probably, due to the second inoculation the previous days. The application of 1% rhamnolipids to the polluted soil resulted increased EOC in the RML and BARML treatments; thereafter, a continuous decrease in EOC reflect the changes due to microbial organic carbon consumption, which was assisted due to biosurfactant application. This effect is largely observed in the BARML treatment, where the addition of the microbial consortium increased the catabolic capacity of native microbial community of this soil. Extractable total N (ETN) were affected in the samples with the bioaugmentation treatment (BA) compared to the controls (CT, BH1, BH2, and RML) without addition of microbial consortium in which there were hardly any variations, as shown in Fig. 1 d. In the evolution of available P levels, an increase was observed after both inoculations, due to the addition of the nutrient solution together with the bioaugmentation, however, decreasing slightly a few days after inoculation, due to nutrient consumption by soil microorganisms and remaining stable, thereafter as shown in Fig. 1 e. It should be noted that in the second inoculation, no significant effect was observed for either the biostimulation or bioaugmentation treatments.

3.2. Biological parameters evolution

Basal soil respiration (BSR) showed a considerable increase during the first 15 days of incubation in the bioaugmentation treatments, due to the increase in both soil and added microbial activity. This increase in basal soil respiration was not the same during the second inoculation even though additional nutrients were also added, perhaps because the assimilable nutrients in the initial soil had already been consumed by the microorganisms, or due to the lack of available hydrocarbons that could be used as a carbon source. These effects are shown in Fig. 2. The control samples (CT, BH1, and BH2) did not change throughout the incubation, and a possible initial inhibitory effect could be shown in the BH1 and BH2 treatments. However, in RML the basal soil respiration increased slightly in both inoculations, showing an increase in the following days.

3.3. Visualization of microbial attachment by environmental scanning electron microscopy

The attachment of the microbial consortium to the biochar particles was visualized by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). As it is shown in

Fig. 3, microorganisms appeared distributed throughout the surface of the BH1 particles. By the same token, BH2 particles displayed a high microbial load in their surface, as depicted in Fig. 4. In both cases, the irregular topography that the surface of the particles increased the available surface area, providing thus a scaffold for the microorganisms that facilitates their adhesion and, consequently, increasing the susceptibility of the biochar particles to be colonized. Due to the nature of biochar and its large number of pores, it is very difficult to quantify the bacteria that colonise it, but it can be stated that bacteria are able to use it as a medium for growth and thus improve their survival.

3.4. Biochar analysis with FTIR-ATR

The BH1 sample colonized by the microbial consortia (BH1_R) and the milled BH1 sample without bacteria (BH1_T) essentially show the same FTIR spectra (Fig. 5a). The bands and their proposed assignments can be summarized as follows. At higher energies, a broad band around 3332 cm^{-1} (band 13 in Fig. 5 a, attributed to stretching OH and, in a lesser extent, to NH vibrations with different origins, probably spread to be involved in hydrogen bonding interactions), a very weak absorption at 3045 cm^{-1} (band 12 in Fig. 5 a, stretching vibrations of aromatic C–H bonds), and three bands placed in the $2950\text{--}2850\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region, characteristic of aliphatic $\nu(\text{CH})$ modes (Kim and Ko, 2020). Around 1690 cm^{-1} there is a shoulder attributed to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ modes in α,β -substituted carbonyl derivatives and aryl ketones (Kim and Ko, 2020). The band in the $1580\text{--}1550\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region can be assigned to cooperative contributions of the $\nu(\text{COO})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ modes, as those in $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C}-\text{COO}^-)$ moieties but is more often ascribed to the antisymmetric stretching vibration $\nu_a(\text{COO}^-)$ in carboxylate groups (Lago et al., 2021). A weak band at 1429 cm^{-1} can be assigned to $\delta(\text{CH})$ vibrations (Li et al., 2007). The weak absorption around 1370 cm^{-1} could be attributed to combinations of $\delta(\text{COH})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ ring modes from in phenyl-rich regions, or to CH vibrations in lignin and polysaccharides (Kim and Ko, 2020), but also to the carboxylate symmetric $\nu_s(\text{COO}^-)$ vibration, as mentioned above. The strong and broad band at 1152 cm^{-1} could be the envelope of absorptions with different origins, as lignin $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{R})$ modes (Moradi-Choghmarani et al., 2019). The band around 1034 cm^{-1} with an unresolved shoulder could be attributed to the presence of ash in the samples (Sharma et al., 2018), as the in-plane stretching Si–O vibration modes in silicate minerals (Fourdrin et al., 2009; Shahverdi-Shahraki et al., 2015), but organic contributions cannot be discarded. The three band pattern observed in the $870\text{--}740\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region could be attributed as a whole to H–C–C rocking vibrations in different aromatic environments (Cooke et al., 1986; Odeh, 2015), being those around $864\text{--}861$

Fig. 2. Basal soil respiration (BSR) of the applied treatments, and evolution along the 90 days. Treatments: CT, control soil, BH1, soil and 5% biochar $450\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, BH2, soil and 5% biochar $600\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$; RML, soil and 1% rhamnolipids; BACT, bioaugmented control soil; BABH1, bioaugmented soil and 5% biochar $450\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$; BABH2, bioaugmented soil and 5% biochar $600\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$; BARML, bioaugmented soil and 1% rhamnolipids. Mean values \pm standard deviation.

Fig. 3. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of BH1 – Biochar without bacterial consortium captured at 40 μm (a), whereas (b) captured at 10 μm , and (c) represent biochar with immobilized bacterial consortium captured at 50 μm , while (d) is captured at 10 μm . The square in (a) and (c) magnified areas used to capture (b) and (d).

cm^{-1} assigned to substituted benzene rings with isolated H atoms, that in the 809–787 cm^{-1} region to substituted benzene rings with two adjacent H atoms and/or condensed ring systems (Cooke et al., 1986) and, finally, the band at 751–740 cm^{-1} could be related to O-substituted benzenes and/or monosubstituted benzene rings. A BH2_R colonized biochar and the sample without cell colonization (BH2_R4C) follow the same trend discussed above for the BH1 samples, but the intensity of the bands in these samples is lower than those in the BH1 biochar derivatives due to the lack of functional groups, being hardly distinguished from the baseline (Fig. 5b).

The nearly identical spectra only exhibit very slight differences that fall inside the resolution limits of the technique. The FTIR spectrum of an RML sample colonized by the microbial consortium (RML_R) is provided in Fig. 5 c, together with the IR spectra of the microbial consortium without biochar or rhamnolipid named as microbial control (Control). Regarding the RML_R spectrum, a medium-strong band at 3275 cm^{-1} is observed, with shoulders about 3390 and 3190 cm^{-1} , which could correspond to stretching $\nu(\text{NH})$ and $\nu(\text{OH})$ modes from proteins and/or other organic molecules, as the hydroxyl groups in the rhamnolipid and carboxylic moieties in the rhamnolipids, and water (band 1 in Fig. 5c). Weak bands around 3070 cm^{-1} can be attributed to aromatic $\nu(\text{CH})$ vibrations (band 2 in Fig. 5c). Medium band at 2954 cm^{-1} , sharp and medium-strong at 2924 cm^{-1} and shoulder at 2870 cm^{-1} together with another sharp absorption at 2853 cm^{-1} is characteristic of aliphatic $\nu(\text{CH})$ modes (bunch of bands labeled as 3 in Fig. 5c). Concretely, that absorption at 2950 cm^{-1} could be assigned to aliphatic $\nu(\text{CH}_3)$ groups, and those between 2925 and 2850 cm^{-1} could involve aliphatic $\nu(\text{CH}_3)$, CH_2 , and CH modes rich in $\nu(\text{CH}_2)$ character (Cooke et al., 1986).

A weak shoulder about 1730 cm^{-1} could be assigned to the carbonyl group in carboxylic acids, esters and/or cyclic ketones (Sharma et al., 2018). A very strong (vs) band with at least two minima can be observed

at 1642 and 1625 cm^{-1} which can be attributed to water bending $\delta(\text{HOH})$ modes overlapped with $\delta(\text{NH}_2)$ and amide I vibrations from peptide content (Sharma et al., 2018). Strong bands appear at 1535 cm^{-1} and in the 1372–1352 cm^{-1} range, which could be due to the antisymmetric and symmetric COO modes of deprotonated carboxylate groups (Li et al., 2007; Li and Chen, 2018), but the influence of the amide II contribution in the former absorption cannot be ruled out. The medium intensity absorption at 1445 cm^{-1} has been attributed to in plane C–O–H bending in the carboxylic group (Li and Chen, 2018; Sharma et al., 2018), but also to bending $\delta(\text{CH})$ aliphatic vibrations (Lago et al., 2021; Li et al., 2007). A medium band at 1238 cm^{-1} could be due to combinations of CH_2 wagging and C–O–H bending modes (Lago et al., 2021). Finally, the very strong band at 1052 cm^{-1} could be attributed to antisymmetric stretching C–O–C modes (Trusovas et al., 2016). The comparison between Control and RML suggests the former is contained in the latter one. The spectra evidence strong analogies above 1000 cm^{-1} , except for the strong band arising at 1352 cm^{-1} in RML. In addition, the shoulder at 1730 cm^{-1} in RML_R are stronger than that in Control. Unfortunately, the comparison between the spectra of RML, BH1_R and BH2_R is revealed as not very informative (Supplementary fig. 1). This lack of significance is ratified in Supplementary fig. 2, where the subtle differences found in the spectra of BH1_R1 and BH1 cannot be interpreted as due to the influence of RML_1.

3.5. Extractable petroleum hydrocarbons quantitative determination

The high molecular weight of extractable petroleum hydrocarbons (EPHs) were from the beginning the predominant fractions of the hydrocarbon mixture contained in the soil under study; the average distribution by chain groups being as follows: C10–C12: 8.7 mg kg^{-1} , C12–C16: 213.3 mg kg^{-1} , C16–C21: 183.3 mg kg^{-1} , C21–C30: 2166.7

Fig. 4. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of BH2 Biochar without bacterial consortium captured at 50 μm (a), whereas (b) captured at 10 μm , and (c) represent biochar with immobilized bacterial consortium captured at 50 μm , while (d) is captured at 10 μm . The square in (a) and (c) magnified areas used to capture (b) and (d).

mg kg^{-1} , C30–C35: 1333.3 mg kg^{-1} , and C35–C40: 370.0 mg kg^{-1} . Therefore, it can be stated that most of the hydrocarbons present in the soil were of a recalcitrant nature (more than 90% with aliphatic chains higher than 21 C atoms), and therefore very difficult to reduce, due to their low availability to the microorganisms that are involved in their biodegradation. Fig. 6 shows the percentage degradation of EPHs. Increased EPHs degradation in the bioaugmentation treatments (BACT, BABH1, BABH2, and BARML) were noted, compared to the treatment in which no BA was provided (CT, BH1, BH2, and RML). Although most of the degradation occurred during the first 30 days, a trend of hydrocarbon degradation was maintained until the end of the incubation, but in the BH1 treatment, it was observed that degradation was not as fast and increased significantly at 90 days. While in the BH2 treatment degradation did not increase from day 30 onwards.

The high resistance of these EPHs to microbial degradation was demonstrated by the results obtained after 90 days of incubation, under ideal humidity, aeration, and temperature conditions. Although significant differences were observed in treatments, where BH1 and BH2 were added, probably due to the population of native soil microorganisms in these amendments, a higher significance was shown when all treatments were bioaugmented with the microbial community. Therefore, it was concluded that at 90 days, higher degradation was achieved with the treatments in which the microbial consortium was inoculated, where degradation percentages of 21.6 for BACT, 27.5 for BABH1, and 29.8 for BABH2 and BARML were achieved. In Fig. 6, it has been shown that all bioaugmentation treatments have biodegraded in the same way, however, in Table 2 it has been shown that this was not the case, and that for long chain hydrocarbons (C21–C30 and C30–C35) the significance of degradation was higher for those treatments in which amendments have been added (BABH1, BABH2, and BARML).

In addition, from different treatments raw data of soil

physicochemical characteristics and total petroleum hydrocarbons, a network analysis was performed to understand the relationships between parameters and the overall variation in the data contributed due to the applied treatment (Supplementary fig. 3). The network study showed a maximum number of possible edges of 36, but not all of them were present in the treatment groups applied in the experiment. The treatment groups corresponding to the controls (CT, BH1, BH2, and RML) contained no edges, however, for the bioaugmentation, treatments 36 edges were observed, the BACT and BARML groups had 24 of these edges, the BABH1 group 23 edges, and the BABH2 group 27 edges. The measure of the degree of network dispersion was highest for BABH1 with a dispersion of 0.361, followed by BACT and BARML with a dispersion of 0.333, and lastly BABH2 with 0.250, indicating that the interactions between the different properties in the bioaugmentation treatments were 63.9%, 66.7% and 75%, respectively (Supplementary table 2 and Supplementary table 3). These high dispersions, the high number of interactions between the different properties indicate that the degradation of hydrocarbons (i.e., the decrease in TPH levels) is unlikely due to direct changes in soil properties (as observed in BH1 and BH2). Instead, it likely arises from the growth of microorganisms that benefit from the organic amendments (BABH1, BABH2, and BARML). The reason for only performing the network analysis with BA treatments is that the most prominent impact on TPHs degradation and other studied parameters are observed in BA treatments - applied individually and combined (Supplementary table 4). The analysis and information provided in Supplementary table 4 complement the Supplementary fig. 1, as the variable that was showing highest variation in data is BA. The studied parameters that are impacted with individual and combined application of variables (BA, BH1, BH2, and RML) can help identify the most important parameter, and the important of association with other parameters. For instance, even though the sparsity of BABH1, BABH2,

Fig. 5. Representative FTIR spectra in the 4000–400 cm^{-1} region of: (a) the BH1_R together with BH1_T (450 °C), with and without microbial consortium, respectively, (b) the BH2_R together with BH2_T (600 °C), with and without microbial consortium, respectively, and (c) RML_R in red, and Control_1 in blue, corresponding to the rhamnolipids and the microbial consortium, respectively. The main differences between them are highlighted in green rectangles. T and Control (BH1-T, BH2-T & Control) correspond to a pulverized sample without bacterial consortia used as a control, and R (BH1_R, BH2_R & RML_R) corresponds to a sample replicate with the bacterial consortia colonized.

and BARML is much higher (Supplementary fig. 1), to draw conclusion from network analysis, the best parameters to study varied. As seen in the Supplementary table 4, the individual application of BA resulted in the significant variation in all the treatments, except in the case of BSR which are also influenced by the indigenous microbial population changes. While individual application of RML, BH1, and BH2 showed impacts on the levels of NO_3 and NH_4 , the individual application of RML also influenced the TC level in soil. This is the indication that the recalcitrant fraction of hydrocarbon in RML being more available, compared to the BH1 and BH2 treatment. The co-application has a combined effect on some parameters. For instance, with BABH1 impacts were noted only on NO_3 , the BABH2 showed impacts on NO_3 and NH_4 , while the BARML combined application showed influence in TC, NO_3 , and NH_4 .

4. Discussion

Soil inoculation with specialized microorganisms is a promising technique that could be useful in the imperative search of mitigating solutions of polluted soil environments. The microbial consortium previously isolated from this contaminated soil by Garrido-Sanz et al. (2019) and Curiel-Alegre et al. (2022a), due to its high TPHs degradation capacity in a soil with multiple sources pollution, is an optimal approach for alleviating the harmful effects of contaminants. The method used for the microorganisms' application is also a pivotal step for the bioremediation of contaminated sites as it has been already explained in depth by Behera et al. (2021). The addition of the bioaugment in two steps, to increase its growth and thus improve its survival are key points to achieve an efficient degradation, so in relation to this study, the preparation of the pre-inoculum to a final concentration of approximately 10^{11} CFU kg^{-1} of soil was necessary to bioaugment the consortia in the optimal conditions for an efficient treatment. For the bioaugmentation treatments, it was higher due to the addition of the nutrient solution, decreasing during the first days of incubation, and increasing later, since microorganisms could not extract it easily at the beginning of the experience, but were more able to assimilate it when changing the soil properties, such as pH. This consumption is higher for the bioaugmentation treatments because the net nutrient consumption is higher, when the soil microorganisms increase, and in turn the microbial growth of the soil microorganisms increases. The success of microbial community capable of biodegrading hydrocarbon within the soil hinges on a complex network orchestrated by environmental and biological factors (Bolan et al., 2023). Soil pH acts as a conductor, influencing like a switch for the crucial enzymes based on its acidity or alkalinity (Piotrowska-Długosz and Charzyński, 2015). Temperature acts like a dimmer, controlling the microbial metabolic rate, while the availability of essential nutrients fuels their growth and biodegradation efforts (Onwuemezie and Darabkhani, 2024). Oxygen availability further complicates the picture, dictating which microbial communities dominate and the specific bacterial arsenals, including aerobic or anaerobic degradation pathways, are employed accordingly (Chicca et al., 2022; Rosa-Masegosa et al., 2024). Finally, the existing indigenous microbial population can act as both competitors and collaborators, influencing the effectiveness of reinforcements like bioaugmentation (Khan and Barros, 2023; Velasco-Arroyo et al., 2024). By unraveling the intricate connections of these interactions, a microbial cooperation can be achieved able to unlock their full potential in cleaning up contaminated environments. Hence, the type of microbial consortium, its growth, and survival are not the only factors that influence hydrocarbon degradation; the degradation process is also affected by environmental and biological factors of the soil, such as pH, temperature, oxygen availability, and nutrient content (Hussain et al., 2022; Parthipan et al., 2022). Therefore, this study was conducted under controlled temperature, aeration, and humidity conditions for the microcosms. The soils in which the bioaugmentation treatments were carried out were enriched with a nutrient solution (BHB) to improve the soil characteristics and the survival of the microorganisms. Moured et al. (2023) also highlighted that the biodegradability of hydrocarbons is closely related to the concentration and bioavailability of nutrients and microelements, something that has been demonstrated in this experiment, with the soil under study being a determining factor due to its high recalcitrance and difficulty for degradation.

The application of amendments to hydrocarbon contaminated soils is a way to improve the different bioremediation techniques commonly used in many studies aimed at the degradation of these pollutants (Ding et al., 2017). For example, the addition of biochar acts as a suitable habitat for the growth of microorganisms, both indigenous from the soil or added in the bioaugmentation strategy, thus accelerating the biodegradation of petroleum hydrocarbons (Zhen et al., 2021), enhancing the ability of indigenous microorganisms to access and further degrade produced short-chain hydrocarbons. Nevertheless,

Fig. 6. Extractable petroleum hydrocarbons (EPHs) degradation percentage along the experiment compared with initial soil (T0). Bars with different letters show significant statistical differences, with small letter showing differences at T30 days, while capital letters at T90 days ($p < 0.05$). Treatments: CT, control soil, BH1, soil and 5% biochar 450 °C, BH2, soil and 5% biochar 600 °C; RML, soil and 1% rhamnolipids; BACT, bioaugmented control soil; BABH1, bioaugmented soil and 5% biochar 450 °C; BABH2, bioaugmented soil and 5% biochar 600 °C; BARML, bioaugmented soil and 1% rhamnolipids.

Table 2

Concentration of the fractions of EPHs from the different treatments at 90 days (T6) compared with initial soil (T0) expressed in mg kg^{-1} .

Technique	Treatment ID	EPH C10–C12	EPH C12–C16	EPH C16–C21	EPH C21–C30	EPH C30–C35	EPH C35–C40
Biostimulation	CT	5.17 ± 0.15	156.67 ± 5.77	143.33 ± 11.55	2100.00 ± 0.00	1233.33 ± 115.47	370.00 ± 0.00
	BH1	5.83 ± 0.78	153.33 ± 5.77	96.50 ± 4.95	2133.33 ± 57.74	1133.33 ± 57.74 *	283.33 ± 15.28
	BH2	5.30 ± 0.35	153.33 ± 11.55	133.33 ± 5.77	2066.67 ± 152.75	1166.67 ± 57.74	285.00 ± 7.07
	RML	5.07 ± 0.55	163.33 ± 5.77	136.67 ± 5.77	2233.33 ± 57.74	1166.67 ± 57.74	283.33 ± 11.55
Bioaugmentation	BA	5.00 ± 0.60	153.33 ± 5.77	125.00 ± 7.07	1633.33 ± 57.74 ***	1100.00 ± 100.00 **	303.33 ± 35.12
	BABH1	6.00 ± 0.00	155.00 ± 7.07	100.50 ± 13.44	1650.00 ± 70.71 ***	986.67 ± 23.09 ***	276.67 ± 20.82
	BABH2	5.37 ± 0.21	150.00 ± 0.00	29.00 ± 0.00	1566.67 ± 115.47 ***	986.67 ± 105.99 ***	273.33 ± 41.63
	BARML	5.33 ± 0.83	150.00 ± 10.00	110.00 ± 10.00	1500.00 ± 173.21 ***	986.67 ± 32.15 ***	270.00 ± 26.46

Columns with different symbols show significant statistical differences, * meaning significant difference at $p \leq 0.05$, ** significant difference at $p \leq 0.01$, and *** significant difference at $p \leq 0.0001$.

encouraging this growth with organic supports such as a biochar can also be significant for the degradation of hydrocarbons, as an enhanced mineralization of recalcitrant components is reached, and with the mineralization of long-chain hydrocarbons is favored when biochar is produced at higher temperatures of pyrolysis (Ling et al., 2022). Bacterial immobilization on this bio-based materials enhances the adsorption, followed by biofilm formation in the inner and outer surface of the biochar, as shown in Figs. 3 and 4. In this stage, the biochar became coarse and distorted, and particle adhesion could be observed in contrast to the clean surface of the control, as expected according to (Feng et al., 2020). A deeper study of the interaction between biochar and bacteria was performed with FTIR-ATR analyses, where no microbial colonization was visualized on BH1 and BH2 by FTIR measurements, probably due to the microbial growth in the surface of the material, produced a signal that fell below the detection limits of the technique. Although the results achieved by this technique are preliminary, it can be stated that the biochar manufacturing conditions such as pyrolysis temperature and the feedstock used can affect the abundance of functional groups present in them, and therefore, the modification of soil properties; it was clearly shown that the abundance of functional groups was lower when the pyrolysis temperature increases (Hussain et al., 2018). Therefore, the original material used for the biochar manufacturing not only affect the form of biochar produced, but it can also have a significant effect on the remediation efficacy of TPHs (Hoang et al., 2021). It can also be stated that the faster is the pyrolysis process, the more abundant functional groups like carboxylic and hydroxyl groups will be, with CH groups being the most abundant in slow pyrolysis (Zama et al., 2018). On the contrary, the same FTIR analysis was done for the interaction between rhamnolipid and bacteria, where most of the IR bands observed in the colonized rhamnolipid RML samples can be attributed to the microbial

consortium. In addition, Zhen et al. (2021) showed how the co-application of a rhamnolipid-modified biochar enhances the degradation of petroleum hydrocarbons, n-alkanes, and PAHs. Although in this way biochar would be improved, to simplify the technique in this study, we have tried to add the amendments separately, achieving similar remediation rates as the previous study, which allows a faster and less economically costly action the remediation of the contaminated soil (Hussain et al., 2018; Khan et al., 2023). Therefore, environmental impact and economic costs must also be considered in this technology; while BH2 improves bacterial immobilization and soil remediation compared to BH1, without reaching significant differences between them, its production results in lower biochar yields when pyrolysis is performed under higher temperatures. In the case of rhamnolipids, they must always be added together with the microbial consortium to influence bioremediation, and their use without bioaugmentation has not led to significant differences with the control in the degradation of hydrocarbons. Numerous studies have demonstrated the capacity of rhamnolipids to help and improve the growth of microorganisms when used in bioaugmentation treatments (Khan et al., 2017). Rong et al. (2021) showed how better results were achieved with rhamnolipids than even with chemical surfactants, however the form of application of rhamnolipids and the nature of these affect the results obtained. Rhamnolipids did not significantly outperform biochars in hydrocarbon degradation likely due to several factors. The recalcitrant nature of the hydrocarbons may limit their ability to desorb and interact with rhamnolipids (Ławniczak et al., 2020). Additionally, available rhamnolipid-hydrocarbon complexes might not be readily utilized by all microbes, and complex soil properties can hinder their effectiveness (Liu et al., 2018). Further, despite the recent increase in interest in bio-surfactants, the market for these substances is still underdeveloped

because of the economics of production and the accessibility to less expensive raw material (Gautam et al., 2023). Hence the high cost, potential toxicity at high doses, and the difficulty in optimizing their application for specific environments limit the practicality of rhamnolipids compared to biochars in large-scale bioremediation efforts (Ashkanani et al., 2024). Thus, although in this study good biodegradation percentages were achieved with the use of rhamnolipids, these did not have significant results in comparison with biochars, which are economically more viable, so the search for more specific biosurfactants for this type of soil will continue in future studies.

However, much work remains to be done to remove long-chain hydrocarbons, which, although significantly reduced in this study, are remained in high quantities, as shown in other studies such as that of Zhen et al. (2021), where degradation of long carbon chains has also been slow, due to the recalcitrant nature of these types of compounds. This may be due not only to the sort of duration of this study and the high molecular weight of these compounds, but also to their hydrophobicity, which makes the pollutant less accessible to both native and bioaugmentation microorganisms. When the expected degradation rates were not achieved (Chen et al., 2017), the consortium previously isolated from the soil was added, but apparently this was not enough to reach a complete mineralization. On the other hand, due to the high concentrations of hydrocarbons of the most recalcitrant fractions, the carbon/nutrient ratios can be affected or even have toxic effects on micro-organisms with biodegradation capacities, thus limiting their growth and degradation activity (Abena et al., 2019). These factors are decisive in understanding how these treatments have achieved significant differences and could lead to even higher degradation rates in the future.

5. Conclusions

This study investigated the efficacy of various bioremediation strategies for tackling hydrocarbon-contaminated soil. Bioaugmentation with a pre-isolated microbial consortium emerged as the most effective approach, achieving significant degradation (22% individually, and up to ~30% when applied in combination with biochar or rhamnolipids) of the highly recalcitrant long-chain hydrocarbons (C21–C35) after 90 days. Network analysis further supported this finding, demonstrating that bioaugmentation treatments led to complex interactions between soil properties, ultimately promoting biodegradation. While biochar addition (both BH1 and BH2) showed promise in enhancing short-chain hydrocarbon degradation, its effectiveness in targeting long-chain fractions was limited. Although rhamnolipids displayed similar degradation rates as biochar, their high economic cost necessitates further exploration of more sustainable and cost-effective biosurfactants. Further research is needed with reference to a) Optimizing bioaugmentation strategies: Exploring alternative inoculation methods, nutrient amendments, and tailored consortium design for enhanced biodegradation of aged and long-chain hydrocarbon degradation, b) Investigating synergistic approaches: by combining bioaugmentation with optimized amendments (natural and synthetic) or exploring novel bioremediation techniques like enzymatic remediation or bioelectrical remediation systems to achieve more efficient and comprehensive degradation, and c) Addressing limitations: Delving deeper into the impact of hydrophobicity and carbon-to-nutrient ratios on biodegradation rates, potentially mitigating these limitations through targeted interventions. By addressing these knowledge gaps and exploring synergistic approaches, significantly improved, efficient, and sustainable bioremediation efforts can be made for tackling historically contaminated soils harboring persistent long-chain hydrocarbon fractions.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sandra Curiel-Alegre: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Dalia de la Fuente-Vivas:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Aqib Hassan Ali Khan:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Javier García-Tojal:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Resources, Methodology, Investigation. **Blanca Velasco-Arroyo:** Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Investigation. **Carlos Rumbo:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Investigation. **Gerhard Soja:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Carlos Rad:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Rocío Barros:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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